

D3.1 BEST PRACTICE LIBRARY

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<p>Abstract</p>	<p>In the context of LEADSx2030 and Advanced Digital Skills, we refer to best practices as successful, inspirational and innovative solutions for addressing the skills gap in Europe by 2030, while also being scalable and transferable across contexts and regions. Best practices will be used to address key challenges, associated with the advanced digital skills gap, by illustrating among others concrete tools, methodologies, frameworks and approaches.</p> <p>Deliverable 3.1 showcases the Best Practice Library developed by LEADSx2030 to serve as a go-to centralised resource for professionals and policymakers dedicated to boosting advanced digital skills across the EU. The Best Practice Library is a searchable and filterable online repository, intended to disseminate key learnings from selected initiatives and actions in the advanced digital skills field. The structured taxonomy, intuitive classification and transparent process for submitting and evaluating best practices is expected to boost knowledge sharing by different stakeholders, including the project's immediate network, other funded actions, training providers, industry and policymakers.</p>
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Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
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- * *R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)*
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc
DMP: Data management plan
ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.
SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues
OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The LEADSx2030 Best Practice Library is a centralised online repository designed to support a wide range of stakeholders in the development and dissemination of advanced digital skills across Europe. Developed under the LEADSx2030 project, this repository will collect and showcase best practices from stakeholders, such as but not limited to public and private training providers, universities, vocational education and training (VET) institutions, research centres, policymakers, and industry experts.

In the context of LEADSx2030 and Advanced Digital Skills, we refer to best practices as successful, inspirational and innovative solutions for addressing the skills gap in Europe by 2030, while also being scalable and transferable across contexts and regions. Best practices will be used to address key challenges, associated with the advanced digital skills gap, by illustrating among others concrete tools, methodologies, frameworks and approaches.

The aim of the repository is to serve as a point-of-reference knowledge-sharing hub, for the wider advanced digital skills ecosystem, promoting the exchange of successful tools, methodologies and frameworks that enhance digital competencies.

Key features of the repository include:

- A structured taxonomy and categorisation to ensure clarity in best practice classification, but also the usability and usefulness of the repository to independent users.
- A streamlined submission and evaluation process enabling external stakeholders to contribute valuable content to the repository.
- Predefined eligibility criteria ensuring that all best practices are relevant, inspiring, solution-driven, impactful and replicable.
- A searchable and filterable online tool available at advancedskills.eu/bestpractices, where users can browse best practices.

This document outlines the criteria for defining best practices, the submission and approval process, and the core components of the repository.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ADS	Advanced Digital Skills
ADSEU	Advanced Digital Skills Europe Platform
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DIGITAL	Digital Europe Programme
DoA	Description of Action
EU-27	European Union 27 Member States
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HR	Human Resources
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SO4	Strategic Objective 4 (Advanced Digital Skills) of the Digital Europe Programme
STEM	Science Technology Engineering Mathematics
VET	Vocational Education Training
WP	Work Package

ABOUT LEADSx2030

LEADSx2030 is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded under the Advanced Digital Skills Strategic Objective 4 (SO4) of the DIGITAL Programme. As a CSA, it is tasked with:

- Delivering insights into the changing advanced digital skills demands in the EU, and determining to what extent the current education and training offers match the needs of the current and future labour market.
- Recommending priority areas for new funding programmes and giving indications on which type of programmes and training is most effective for building up advanced digital skills.
- Supporting excellence in education and training institutions, aiming at the development of a dynamic digital education and training ecosystem.
- Promoting collaboration among the SO4 Cluster, i.e. the consortia awarded from the different call topics under the DIGITAL SO4.

As such, over a period of 48 months LEADSx2030 will:

- Provide a continuous review of demand and supply changes related to advanced digital skills.
- Map the outputs of the SO4 Cluster to identify key results and success stories.
- Develop the SO4 Cluster into a dynamic network.
- Provide opportunities for synergies with relevant European actors.
- Bring all stakeholders together in point-of-reference annual advanced digital skills summits.
- Support the strategic EU policy objectives through targeted analyses and recommendations.

In this context, the Best Practice Library (D3.1) is an example of a tool developed by LEADSx2030 to support the development of the SO4 Cluster into a dynamic network, through the dissemination of success stories, exchange of knowledge and promotion of synergies.

Latest information about the initiative can be found at www.advancedskills.eu.

DIGITAL SO4 ADS CLUSTER

The DIGITAL programme was conceived with the aim of empowering citizens with advanced digital skills and preparing them to tackle current societal challenges. Up to 2024, it has invested €287M for actions on advanced digital skills in key capacity areas within the 2021- 2027 period.

In terms of advanced digital skills, the DIGITAL programme’s Strategic Objective 4 (SO4) states:

“Advanced Digital Skills shall support the development of Advanced Digital Skills in areas covered by the Programme in order to contribute to increasing Europe’s talent pool, bridge the digital divide and foster greater professionalism, especially with regard to high performance and cloud computing, big data analytics, cybersecurity, distributed ledger technologies, quantum technologies, robotics, artificial intelligence, while taking gender balance into account.”¹

Under the SO4 there is an extensive portfolio of 45 projects (Figure 1), focused on the delivery of new advanced digital skills programmes. These include specialised master’s programmes and courses, short-term training courses, a cybersecurity skills academy, programmes for reinforcing skills in semiconductors, and a EuroHPC training platform for high-performance computing.

Table 1. Types and scale of actions in the SO4 Cluster²

Topic code	No. projects	Duration	EU funding	Total budget ³
Specialised education programmes and courses in key capacity areas				
DIGITAL-2021-SKILLS-01-SPECIALISED	8	2022-2026	€56.5M	€103M
DIGITAL-2022-SKILLS-03-SPECIALISED-EDU	12	2023-2027	€78.2M	€125.5M
DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-05-SPECIALAEDU	5	2024-2029	€32.6M	€35.3M
Short-term training courses in key capacity areas				
DIGITAL-2022-TRAINING-02-SHORT-COURSES	12	2022-2025	€24.3M	€40.5M
Cybersecurity skills academy				
DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-05-CYBERACADEMY	5	2024-2027	€11.7M	€22.8M
Reinforcing skills in semiconductors				
DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-04-CHIPS	2	2024-2028	€9.1M	€18.3M
EuroHPC training platform				
DIGITAL-EUROHPC-JU-2022-TRAINING-02	1	2024-2025	€2M	€2M
Total	45	2022-2029	€214.4M	€347.4M

The main target areas, for which these programmes aim to improve the supply of advanced digital skills, include cybersecurity, Artificial Intelligence (AI), manufacturing and infrastructure, business innovation, SMEs and digital health. Other notable areas are energy and sustainability, public administration, and semiconductors.

More information on the Cluster projects can be found at the [Digital Europe Programme dashboard](#).

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2022/2481/oj>

² The following table includes the funded actions under the remit of LEADSx2030, and not necessarily all actions funded under Strategic Objective 4.

³ These numbers account for the total EU-funding requested and the total investment including co-funding from other sources and private investment.

1 Introduction

The Best Practice Library (D3.1) developed by BluSpecs is a public online repository drawing on best practices from the SO4 Cluster projects. It will be hosted on the project website and allow for users to search for best practices by type and other relevant categories. It will serve as a centralised, accessible resource that compiles identified best practices in the advanced digital skills landscape.

Its content will provide information about and key takeaways from the implementation of innovative tools, methodologies, frameworks and approaches deployed by stakeholders to promote the development of advanced digital skills in Europe. These stakeholders include leading universities, Vocational Education and Training (VET) providers, research centres, policymakers, industry experts and practitioners, among others.

The aim of this public repository is to support existing and future efforts in developing critical digital competencies across the EU-27. By disseminating these best practices, the repository aims to foster a culture of knowledge exchange, empowering European industry to stay competitive and thrive in the digital age. On a higher level, the repository aspires to become a reference resource for advanced digital skills, that will be used by various stakeholder communities beyond the LEADSx2030 project and SO4 Cluster projects.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document does not represent the Best Practice Library itself but is to register its publication through the following link: advancedskills.eu/best-practice-repository/

The purpose of the report is to outline the process for submitting best practices as external users of the LEADSx2030 website and provide concrete criteria for defining best practices. These criteria will be used as reference for evaluating and approving incoming content.

1.2 Target audience

Among the intended users of the LEADSx2030 best practice repository are, both public and private training providers, policymakers, industry and SMEs. The use case of this repository is to permit all users to easily contribute and/or access best practices that would support their activities or participation in developing advanced digital competencies.

The general public is an indirect target stakeholder group of the repository; users will be able to browse best practices and discover the range of initiatives taking place across Europe, as well as their intended outcomes and beneficiaries.

2 Best practices

WHAT ARE THEY?

Best practices are generally defined as sets of tasks, actions and procedures that are proven to lead to optimal efficiency and results in their respective field. In the context of Advanced Digital Skills, they are expected to include successful, inspirational and innovative solutions for addressing the skills gap in Europe by 2030, while also being scalable and transferable across contexts and regions. Best practices will be used to address key challenges, associated with the advanced digital skills gap, by illustrating concrete tools, methodologies, frameworks and approaches in areas including but not limited to:

- Identifying the most significant needs and demands for advanced and emerging digital skills.
- Designing and implementing educational and training programmes across national borders.
- Upskilling and reskilling of the workforce.
- Improving frameworks for digital competence development tracking and recognition.
- Increasing peer-learning opportunities and knowledge exchange.
- Addressing advanced digital skills development through effective policies on a regional, national and European level.
- Promoting multistakeholder and particularly industry engagement in the design and execution of relevant initiatives.

WHO ARE THEY FOR?

As such, best practices are targeted to a variety of stakeholders, all of which have key roles in leading institutions and organisations and hold decision-making power to implement the proposed solutions and endorse fundamental change in their respective area of activity. These include managers and influential profiles within public and private training institutions, industrial organisations, as well as policymakers on regional, national and European levels. Individual learners and the general public, although considered direct beneficiaries from the best practices, are not included in the target stakeholder groups, as they are not in a position to implement them.

2.1 Minimum content requirements

In order to be eligible for publication on the LEADSx2030 repository, a best practice must be precise and replicable, and provide sufficient information in regard to:

- **The context:** Every best practice must clearly describe to independent users of the repository the background in which it was developed and implemented. This includes an explanation of the setting, key stakeholders and initial conditions.
- **The challenge:** Every best practice must describe very specifically the challenge addressed and how that challenge links to its specific context.
- **The identified solution:** Every best practice must describe the identified solution or approach and the specific actions taken to tackle the challenge. A solution might be tackling multiple challenges, but only one solution can be covered by a single best practice.
- **The outcomes:** Every best practice must be able to demonstrate positive outcomes achieved through the implementation of the relevant actions. Outcomes can be either quantitative or qualitative but must always be concrete.
- **The takeaways:** Every best practice must provide learnings, i.e. specific elements adopted during the implementation of the aforementioned solution that contributed to achieving positive outcomes. Takeaways should be replicable so as to facilitate users who are set to implement the same or similar solution in a relevant context.

A valid best practice should also feature a representative **title**, and be associated with at least one **author**, **project** and/or **organisation**.

In addition, it must feature all of the following elements, for which specific predefined options are provided by LEADSx2030 (Annex 1): Intended users; Beneficiaries; Theme; Action.

2.2 Eligibility criteria

Table 2. Best practice eligibility criteria

Best practice eligibility criteria	Yes/No
Relevance	
Is the solution specific to advanced digital skills challenges or developments?	
Does it focus on practical application rather than theoretical knowledge?	
Does it have a specific target audience?	
Timeliness	
Was the content developed within the past three years?	
Is it expected to be relevant for at least the next five years?	
Quality and credibility	
Does the author of the content have significant experience in the respective topic?	
Is the content developed or endorsed by credible experts, institutions or organisations?	
Impact	
Does the content have measurable outcomes?	
Does the content include practical examples and concrete takeaways?	
Is an associate online resource provided, where users can find further information?	
Scalability and transferability	
Can the content be adapted or scaled across different domains?	
Is it relevant and applicable across Member States?	
Is it designed to be reusable or modifiable for different learning contexts?	

2.3 Best practice collection

LEADSx2030 aims for the repository to become a flagship tool and reference source of best practices for a variety of challenges present within advanced digital skills development. To this end, the best practices and sequentially the repository have been designed and structured so as to address the diversity and heterogeneity of both the targets and the means. In addition to the structuring and categorisation (see sections 3.1, 3.2), this decision is also reflected in the best practice collection. To facilitate the process and ensure the quality of new materials submitted to the repository, a Microsoft form has been created. This can be accessed directly via [this link](#), but also through the LEADSx2030 website [advancedskills.eu/best-practice-repository/].

The full process from submission to approval or rejection (Figure x) involves the following steps:

- Best practices collected via the aforementioned form will be filtered by WP3 contributor and sub-cluster manager (UPM) based on a preliminary author and organisation check, and against the pre-defined minimum content requirements.
- Best practices submitted by ineligible authors or organisations will be rejected, while the remaining ones will be filtered against the minimum content requirements (see section 2.1).
- If these requirements are met, the best practices will be reviewed in more depth in terms of content and against the eligibility criteria (see section 2.2) by the WP3 lead (BluSpecs). Otherwise, the provider will be contacted for complementary inputs.

- Depending on the outcome of the review, the WP3 lead (BluSpecs) will either reject the best practice, contact the provider for more inputs or pass to T6.2 lead to upload on the repository.

Figure 1. Best practice submission process

To update a previously submitted best practice, the provider will have to indicate that in the relevant field included in the best practice submission form.

2.3.1 Target sources of best practices

The best practice submission form is publicly accessible via the LEADSx2030 website. However, to ensure the quality and credibility of published best practices, a key part of the eligibility criteria above, we have identified specific stakeholder groups that could be potential providers of high-quality best practices. These stakeholders can be from across EU-27 as well as from other DIGITAL associated countries.⁴ Best practices from non-associated countries will still be considered, but the content will need to be highly relevant for the European context. The identified target stakeholder groups include:

Training providers (public)

- Universities
- Vocational education and training (VET) institutions
- RTOs
- Regional and local government initiatives

Training providers (private)

- Corporate training providers
- IT certification providers
- Online learning platforms
- Digital skills academies
- NGOs focused on training, upskilling, reskilling

Policymakers

- Regional
- National
- EU

Industry (and SMEs)

- Large companies with specialised HR departments
- Large and medium-sized companies with extensive experience in training programme design and/or execution

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/digital/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_digital_en.pdf

More specifically from the project's ecosystem expected sources of best practices include:

- EU-funded and co-funded projects, particularly from DIGITAL SO4 advanced digital skills.
- Any participants of the LEADSx2030 sub-clusters, which may not belong to the above cluster, such as members of organisations or projects with experience that is highly relevant to the topic of the sub-clusters and are brought in to support the cluster in identifying and implementing best practices.
- Participants of the annual advanced digital skills summits and other LEADSx2030 events.

Pending approval from EC

3 ADS Best practice structure

As explained in section 2.1, collected best practices will share five core components (minimum content requirements), intended to guide best practice providers in selecting all the necessary information to include, in a structured, coherent way. These components are outlined below, along with a short description and their anticipated format.

3.1 Core components

Table 3. Core components of a best practice

Component	Description	Format
Context	Background information on the project, initiative or action within which the best practice was identified.	Paragraph
Challenge	Specific challenges or issues related to the action that need to be addressed or overcome to grasp the benefits of the best practice.	Paragraph
Identified solution	The approach to addressing the challenges or issues that have been identified	Paragraph
Outcomes	Results from the implementation of the best practice	Bullet points, figures
Key takeaways	Lessons, learnings and reflections from going through the action.	Bullet points
Associated resource	Link to relevant resource, such as toolkit, publication, learning material, event page, where users can learn more about the proposed best practice.	URL

3.2 Proposed taxonomy and categorisation

Usability was central to the repository design, as we wanted to provide a tool that is searchable and filterable. Achieving this required the classification of content based on common categories, that would be of use to potential repository users, without overcomplicating the development and evaluation of best practices. A key consideration during the scoping process, was to keep the categories broad enough for best practice providers to easily classify their best practices, even though they might address different topics, contexts, audiences and purpose, but also specific enough to direct users navigating the repository.

The following categories (see section 3.2.1) have been formed on the basis of:

- The ongoing data analysis in LEADSx2030.
- Preliminary discussions in the LEADSx2030 sub-cluster groups.
- Topics brought to our attention by the European Commission and HaDEA.
- Additional desk research.

Nonetheless, all categories will be revised according to new data-based findings, recommendations made in the LEADSx2030 sub-clusters, as well as feedback received through the submission form. This agile approach links back to the objective of rendering the repository a reference source of best practices for a variety of topics and stakeholders within the wider advanced digital skills ecosystem.

3.2.1 List of categories

The best practices are categorised based on the following elements:

Theme: The area of developing advanced digital skills that the best practice contributes towards. [Select one option]

Table 4. Best practice themes

Reskilling and Upskilling	Cross-border Initiatives
Industry Engagement	Women in Digital
Accreditation and Certification	Programme Development
Very Advanced Skills	Skills Data

Action: The type of action performed that led to the identification and registration of the practice. [Select one option]

Table 5. Types of action associated with the best practices

Professional Training	Policy/Guideline
Education Programmes/Courses	Awareness Raising
Work Placement	Facilitating Employment
Framework/Methodology	Stakeholder Collaboration

Intended Users: Stakeholders that are expected to replicate the proposed action. [Select one or more options]

Table 6. Intended users for the Best Practice Library

Training providers (public)	Policymakers (EU)	Industry
Training providers (private)	Policymakers (Member State)	SMEs

Beneficiaries: Stakeholders that will directly benefit from the implementation of the proposed action. [Select one or more options]

Table 7. Beneficiaries from the implementation of the best practices

Training providers (public)	Industry	Labour force (employed)
Training providers (private)	SMEs	Labour force (unemployed)
Policymakers (EU)	Learners (STEM background)	Women
Policymakers (Member State)	Learners (non-STEM)	

4 Online repository

The Best Practice Library can be accessed at advancedskills.eu/best-practice-repository/.

Figure 2. Best Practice Library overview

Welcome to the Best Practice Library for professionals and policymakers dedicated to boosting Europe's Advanced Digital Skills. Explore innovative tools, methodologies, frameworks and approaches implemented by credible experts, organisations and projects in the field of Advanced Digital Skills.

The featured best practices cover topics including but not limited to:

- Advanced Digital Skills demand monitoring
- Education and training programme development
- Industry engagement in education and training programme development
- Upskilling and reskilling for professionals
- Accreditation and certification of Advanced Digital Skills programmes and courses
- Participation of girls and women in Advanced Digital Skills

Are you an active professional in Advanced Digital Skills? Have you identified a best practice within your project or organisation that you would like to share on our library?

Fill in the following form to submit your own best practices.

[SUBMIT YOUR APPLICATION HERE](#)

Search posts...

Themes	Countries	Action
All <input type="button" value="v"/>	All <input type="button" value="v"/>	All <input type="button" value="v"/>
Associated resources	Intended Users	Beneficiaries
All <input type="button" value="v"/>	All <input type="button" value="v"/>	All <input type="button" value="v"/>

Sort

Policymakers (EU)
 Training providers (public) Other
 Framework / Methodology
 Training providers (private)
 Training providers (public) EU
 Accreditation and Certification

A Joint European Degree label in Engineering to facilitate accreditation

📅 14, Feb 2025

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Training providers (public)
 Learning resource
 Education Programmes / Courses
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 Learning resource
 Framework / Methodology
 Stakeholder Collaboration
 Labour force (employed)
 Labour force (unemployed)
 Learners (non-STEM background)
 Austria
 Accreditation and Certification

Assessing and recognising individually acquired digital competencies through the digital skills profile platform

📅 13, Feb 2025

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Figure 3. Overview of filters

Figure 5. Examples of best practices

These examples reflect previously collected best practices which have been updated to reflect the structure and requirements of the LEADSx2030 Best Practice Library.

4.1 Best practice submission form

The best practice submission form can be accessed via [this link](#), but also through the LEADSx2030 website [advancedskills.eu/best-practice-repository/]. For the full list of fields included in the form, see Annex 2.

ANNEX 1 – BEST PRACTICE TAXONOMY

THEME	ACTION	BENEFICIARIES	INTENDED USERS	ASSOCIATED RESOURCES
Reskilling and Upskilling	Professional Training	Training providers (public)	Training providers (public)	Toolkit
Industry Engagement	Education Programmes/Courses	Training providers (private)	Training providers (private)	Publication
Cross-border Initiatives	Work Placement	Policymakers (EU)	Policymakers (EU)	Learning resource
Women in Digital	Framework/Methodology	Policymakers (Member State)	Policymakers (Member State)	Case study
Programme Development	Policy/Guideline	Industry	Industry	Event
Skills Data	Awareness Raising	SMEs	SMEs	Other
Accreditation and Certification	Facilitating Employment	Learners (STEM background)		
Very Advanced Skills	Stakeholder Collaboration	Learners (non-STEM background)		
		Labour force (employed)		
		Labour force (unemployed)		
		Women		

ANNEX 2. BEST PRACTICE SUBMISSION FORM

Section 1 - Best practice description

1. Give a title to your good practice for XXX?

The title should be specific and representative of the content you provide in this form. It should help external readers understand the focus at a glance and decide whether the good practice is relevant for them.

Answer:

2. Context

Describe the background in which your good practice was developed. Explain the setting, key stakeholders and initial conditions.

Answer:

3. Challenge

Describe very specifically the challenge you faced and how it links to your context.

Indicative examples:

- *Conflicting regulations and timetables for accreditation of new master's degrees in Finland and Greece led to delayed programme commencement.*
- *Limited human resources in Spanish SMEs contributed to low engagement of domain-expert professionals in designing and delivering work placement programmes in AI roles.*

Answer:

4. Identified Solution

Describe the solution you identified and/or the approach you followed to overcome the challenge.

Answer:

5. Outcomes

What was achieved through the implementation of the aforementioned solution? Outcomes can be either quantitative or qualitative improvement, but they must be concrete.

Indicative examples:

- *Official accreditation for new master's degree achieved within 10 months of the application.*
- *10% increase in participation of women in our AI training programme.*
- *More positive outlook of employees towards upskilling courses reflected by informal feedback to HR.*

Answer:

6. Key Takeaways

What can readers learn from the way you implemented the solution? Think of specific elements that contributed to achieving those positive outcomes. Takeaways should be replicable in similar contexts.

Answer:

Section 2 - Additional information

1. Main Author(s)

Who are the authors of the good practice? They will be our main contact points for any clarifications or adjustments required.

Answer:

2. Contributor(s)

Add here the full name of other contributors that should be credited for identifying or putting together the best practice. They will appear on the repository as contributors.

Answer:

3. Project(s) or organisation(s)

What projects or organisations is the good practice associated to?

Answer:

4. Country(-ies)

In which countries was your good practice implemented. Write EU if implemented on an EU-level.

Answer:

5. Intended users

Which stakeholders do you anticipate to replicate the proposed action? Select all that apply.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Training providers (public)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Training providers (private)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policymakers (EU)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policymakers (Member State)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Industry
<input type="checkbox"/>	SMEs
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other

6. Beneficiaries

Which stakeholders will directly benefit from the implementation of the proposed action? Select all that apply.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Training providers (public)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Training providers (private)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policymakers (EU)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policymakers (Member State)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Industry

	SMEs
	Learners (STEM background)
	Learners (non-STEM background)
	Labour force (employed)
	Labour force (unemployed)
	Women
	Other

7. Theme

Select the theme/topic that best covers the scope of your good practice.

	Skills data
	Very advanced skills
	Programme development
	Accreditation and certification
	Reskilling and upskilling
	Cross-border initiatives
	Women in digital
	Industry engagement
	Other

9. Action

What did you deliver that led to the identification and registering of your good practice?

	Professional training
	Education programmes / courses
	Work placement
	Framework / methodology
	Policy / guideline
	Awareness raising
	Facilitating employment

	Stakeholder collaboration
	Other

10. Associated resources

Where can readers learn more about your good practice?

	Toolkit
	Publication
	Learning resource
	Case study
	Event
	Other

11. Associated resources

Please provide the link to the resource. Readers will be redirected to this resource for further information.

Answer:

12. Is this content associated with a previously submitted best practice?

Select yes if you would like to update an existing best practice rather than submit a new one.

	Yes
	No